

Astronomers in Babylon

By Gil Breger, University of California, Berkeley

Entry tags: Religious Group, Near East, Mesopotamian Religions, Babylonian Religions

Scribes residing in Babylon and associated with the Esagila, the temple of Marduk in Babylon, and producing numerous kinds of astronomical texts, most prominently the Astronomical Diaries and the mathematical astronomical texts (referred to as ACT in modern scholarship). Their collective identity and their capacity, particularly early on, is not entirely clear. Initially, these scribes were most likely part of the prebendary system, an inherited, part-time privilege in which certain families and individuals had duties to serve the gods on certain days of the month or the year, including but not exclusively celestial observation. In return, they were given a share of the temple offerings. Following the failed rebellion against Persian rule in the 5th century, the prebendary system was abolished. After a period of recuperation, the Esagila was re-organized and governed by guild-like professional associations, one of which bore the title of “scribes of Enūma Anu Enlil” (the celestial omens series), the closest equivalent to the term “astronomer” in the cuneiform record. These individuals received some kind of monthly payment referred to as *kurummatu-rations*.

Date Range: 750 BCE - 80 CE

Region: Babylon

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia, Babylonia

Area of the city of Babylon.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Haubold J., J. Steele., and K. Stevens. *Keeping Watch in Babylon: The Astronomical Diaries in Context*. Leiden: Brill, 2019.
- Source 2: Steele, J. M. "The Circulation of Astronomical Knowledge between Babylon and Uruk." In *The Circulation of Astronomical Knowledge in the Ancient World*, edited by J. M. Steele, 83-118. Leiden: Brill, 2016.
- Source 3: Rochberg, F. "Scribes and Scholars: The *ṭupšār* Enūma Anu Enlil." In *Assyriologica et Semitica, Festschrift für Joachim Oelsner anlässlich seines 65. Geburtstages am 18 Februar 1997*, edited by J. Marzahn and H. Neumann, 359-375. AOAT 252. Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 2000.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/adsd/index.html>

Notes: An online lemmatized edition of the Astronomical Diaries, produced by astronomers, mostly in Babylon.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the vast majority of their authoritative sources were written, in some cases it seems that there was an added component that is not apparent in the written sources.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Often, scholarly texts were attributed to Ea/Enki, the god of wisdom. In particular, aspects of scholarly knowledge related to the sky was sometimes referred to as the wisdom of An/Anu, the sky-god.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Knowledge and wisdom (though not directly astronomy) is sometimes associated with Adapa, a mythological human servant of the god Ea/Enki, or the apkallu, wise sages.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: Generally speaking, there is a sense of secrecy involving knowledge (not specifically astronomy).

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: To the extent that affiliation was passed down within a given family, a father would normally train his sons or members of his extended family.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Persian and then the Hellenistic conquest of Babylon brought the religious traditions of Babylon in contact with those of the Persia and Greece respectively.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The paramount position of the Zoroastrian Ahura Mazda may have served to stimulate and re-invigorate the cult of the Mesopotamian sky-god Anu, and consequently the importance

of celestial observations.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):
– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):
– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Throughout its history, the temple complex was the center of a Mesopotamian city. The complex included structures of varying sizes, from small shrines to towering ziggurats. Due to the change of its importance over time, the extent of the Esagila in Babylon changed over time. Furthermore, astronomers also lived outside the temple complex itself, and kept and produced astronomical texts at their houses.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: After 484 BCE (the rebellion against Xerxes), when prosopographical evidence is more forthcoming, their number was probably a couple of dozens. Earlier, however, their number was likely higher, due to the less specialized nature of their temple duties.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):
– Yes

Notes: In some of the cases, there is a clear familial association. Early in the chronological timespan, affiliation was part of the hereditary prebendary system. There are also examples of a father-son relationship between practitioners.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by class:
– Yes

Notes: Association with this group was often based on familial ties.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although, the education of a scribe takes many years and starts very early.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence for any female astronomer.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Expertise in certain fields of knowledge

Notes: In order to belong to this group, without a doubt practitioners needed to reach a certain level of expertise in scholarship (ṭupšarrūtu), particularly aspects relevant for the practice of astronomy-astrology.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional markers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The astronomers were associated with the temple, and not directly patronized by the rulers. In particular, in the 6th century, the Babylonian king Nabonidus withheld support from the Esagila in an effort to draw it of its political influence, a trend that continued for most of the existence of this group. Seleucid rulers, however, occasionally provided nominal support to the temple, which in turn supported the astronomers.

Is iconography present:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unknown how and where celestial observation exactly took place.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Persian and then the Hellenistic conquest of Babylon brought the religious traditions of Babylon in contact with those of the Persia and Greece respectively.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

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Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: After 484 BCE (the rebellion against Xerxes), when prosopographical evidence is more forthcoming, their number was probably a couple of dozens. Earlier, however, their number was likely higher, due to the less specialized nature of their temple duties.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

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↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: To the extent that affiliation was passed down within a given family, a father would normally train his sons or members of his extended family.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Throughout its history, the temple complex was the center of a Mesopotamian city. The complex included structures of varying sizes, from small shrines to towering ziggurats. Due to the change of its importance over time, the extent of the Esagila in Babylon changed over time. Furthermore, astronomers also lived outside the temple complex itself, and kept and produced astronomical texts at their houses.

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– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional markers:

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↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unknown how and where celestial observation exactly took place.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It does not seem that this group had any social norms that were markedly different that stems from their identification of astronomers.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Punishment (and proper conduct) was not part of the purview of the astronomers in Babylon.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

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– No

Notes: Punishment (and proper conduct) was not part of the purview of the astronomers in Babylon.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It does not seem that this group had any social norms that were markedly different that stems from their identification of astronomers.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The preserved sources do not mention any such practice.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: The preserved sources do not mention any such practice.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: The preserved sources do not mention any such practice.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: The preserved sources do not mention any such practice.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: The preserved sources do not mention any such practice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as it comes to observational texts, conducting observation at night was required.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: The preserved sources do not mention any such practice.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: There is some evidence that, at least in some cases, these scribes were also in charge of conducting rituals related to astronomical events, such as averting the danger foretold by eclipses.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Particularly later in their existence, astronomers in Babylon were required to show a certain level of competency and were organized around guild-like associations.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

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↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Education was likely done in an apprenticeship model, often a father training his sons.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Female scribes were very rare in Mesopotamia in general, and there is no evidence for a female astronomer (albeit, the prosopographical evidence in general is quite sparse).

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly in the later part of its existence, participants were part of a guild-like association.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Early on, when still part of the prebendary system, this group was able to draw on temple land and resources for income.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The astronomical texts were incredibly technical and so required specific knowledge of how to read them.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Some types of astronomical texts used a schematic 360-days year (e.g. MUL.APIN), while other texts employ a luni-solar calendar.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– Yes

Notes: The temple provided for these individuals, first as part of the prebendary system, and then in the form of some kind of rations, called kurummatu-rations.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some astronomical texts employed a schematic "scholarly" calendar of 360-days a year. Other astronomical texts used a luni-solar calendar. In particular, after the conquest of Mesopotamia by Alexander the Great, the Seleucid Era used a continuous year count as well as a 19-year intercalation cycle (the so-called Metonic cycle).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Once the Esagila organized around guild-like professional associations, the astronomers were just one such group.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that these astronomers were in a similar situation as other members of society.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Education was likely done in an apprenticeship model, often a father training his sons.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Female scribes were very rare in Mesopotamia in general, and there is no evidence for a female astronomer (albeit, the prosopographical evidence in general is quite sparse).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly in the later part of its existence, participants were part of a guild-like association.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Once the Esagila organized around guild-like professional associations, the astronomers were just one such group.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Early on, when still part of the prebendary system, this group was able to draw on temple land and resources for income.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that these astronomers were in a similar situation as other members of society.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The astronomical texts were incredibly technical and so required specific knowledge of how to read them.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Some types of astronomical texts used a schematic 360-days year (e.g. MUL.APIN), while other texts employ a luni-solar calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some astronomical texts employed a schematic "scholarly" calendar of 360-days a year. Other astronomical texts used a luni-solar calendar. In particular, after the conquest of Mesopotamia by Alexander the Great, the Seleucid Era used a continuous year count as well as a 19-year intercalation cycle (the so-called Metonic cycle).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The temple provided for these individuals, first as part of the prebendary system, and then in the form of some kind of rations, called kurummatu-rations.